

SOURCES USED BY MUHAMMAD VAFO KARMINAGI IN TUHFAT AL-KHANI

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Since Muhammad Vafo Karminagi's work *Tuhfat al-khani* is the first historical source to depict the events and developments during the transition of power in the Bukhara Khanate from the Ashtarkhanid to the Manghit dynasty, information about its sources is of particular importance. The author wrote *Tuhfat al-khani* based on events he personally witnessed. At the same time, he made efforts to enrich the work using various types of sources. In some instances, the author explicitly mentioned these sources, while in others, he did not acknowledge them.

Regarding the sources of *Tuhfat al-khani*, it should be noted that Muhammad Vafo Karminagi primarily relied on two types of sources while composing his work:

1. **Official court documents:** decrees, edicts, reports, diplomatic letters, and the memoirs of eyewitnesses of the time;
2. **Oral testimonies** of participants in the events, as well as the author's own experiences and observations.

It is evident throughout the pages of the work that the author mainly based his writing on the first group—official documents. It is well known from historical literature that letters and court records served as the primary sources for historians who worked in court positions such as scribes, secretaries, judges, and other officials.

“In *Tuhfat al-khani*, the author likewise drew attention to this type of source material and enriched the text of the work accordingly. Among these sources are:

1. A letter written by Muhammad Hakimbiy, the governor of Qarshi, to Abulfayz Khan concerning the invasion led by the Iranian Rizaquli¹;
2. A letter from Nadir Shah to Abulfayz Khan concerning the uprising in Bukhara led by Ibadulloh Khitoyi²;
3. A letter sent by Muhammad Rahim to Abulfayz Khan on June 23, 1747³;
4. A decree issued by Muhammad Rahim Khan regarding the organization of defensive measures in Bukhara in response to the attack by Iranian Qizilbash troops⁴;

¹ Муҳаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат-ул-хонӣ. Муқаддима, таҳияи матн, нусхабадал, таълиқот ва фехристҳои Чамшад Ҷӯразода ва Нурулло Ғиёсов. Хўҷанд, 2017. – Баргаи 43; ¹ محمد قاضى وفا كرمينگى. تحفة الخانى يا تريخ رحيم خانى. ۱۰۸ ص. دكتور منصور صفت گل استاد دانشگاه تهران با همكارى دكتور نوبواكى كندو. موسسه مطالعات زبانها و فرهنگهاى آسيا و افريكا. فوجو، توكيو. ۲۰۱۳ ص. ۷۶

² Муҳаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат ул-хонӣ. Баргаи 65; ۱۰۸ ص. محمد قاضى وفا كرمينگى. تحفة الخانى يا تريخ رحيم خانى. ۱۰۸ ص.

³ Муҳаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат ул-хонӣ. Баргаи 109; ۱۷۳ ص. محمد قاضى وفا كرمينگى. تحفة الخانى يا تريخ رحيم خانى. ۱۷۳ ص.

⁴ Муҳаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат ул-хонӣ. Баргаи 121; ۱۹۰ ص. محمد قاضى وفا كرمينگى. تحفة الخانى يا تريخ رحيم خانى. ۱۹۰ ص.

5. A decree issued by Muhammad Rahim Khan regarding the construction of the Ark fortress in the city of Qarshi, located in the Nasaf region⁵.

This raises the question: where did Muhammad Vafo Karminagi see and obtain these documents? First and foremost, his service at the court of Muhammad Rahim Khan gave him direct access to such materials. His involvement in court affairs naturally facilitated his use of official documents as needed for his work. Furthermore, it is quite plausible that when Muhammad Rahim Khan commissioned Muhammad Vafo Karminagi to write the chronicle, he granted him broad access to the court archives.

In addition, Muhammad Vafo Karminagi also points to other methods by which he accessed court documents. In certain cases, he notes that letters prepared under the ruler's orders were handed over to him specifically for inclusion in the text. One example of this is when the author includes the full text of a decree issued by Muhammad Rahim Khan after a campaign against Toghaymurodbiy Burqut, in which rebellious traitors were granted amnesty. The author explicitly states that this was done at the ruler's command and incorporated into Tuhfat al-khani⁶.

At the same time, it is known that the author, while writing Tuhfat al-khani, referenced written memoirs of event participants in several places. In particular, regarding Muhammad Rahim Khan's 1749 military campaign against Toghaymurod Burqut, the author notes that when the emir's forces reached the Karmana region, the number of troops increased due to the joining of soldiers from Qarshi, Qorakul, and Turkmens from the Amu Darya riverbanks. He explains this information as coming from "a letter received by the author of this book from trusted friends"⁷.

Additionally, among the historical sources, Muhammad Vafo utilized the works of Mirzo Mahdikhon Astrobodiy's Tarikhi Jahankushoyi Nodiriy and Muhammad Qozim Marviy's Tarikhi Olamuroyi Nodiriy, which are important sources shedding light on Nadir Shah's activities and his invasion of the Bukhara Khanate. Although he does not explicitly mention this anywhere in the text, when describing the details of the Iranian Shah's death, he cites examples from the works of Muhammad Ali Tusiy, one of Nadir Shah's court historians, stating that "Firdawsi Sani, who wrote Nadir Shah's historical chronicle, wove this unexpected event into a poetic couplet, capturing the memory in two verses"⁸.

⁵ Мухаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат ул-хонӣ. Баргаи 198; ۳۰۲. ص. محمد قاضى وفا كرمينگى. تحفة الخانى يا تريخ رحيم خانى.

⁶ Мухаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат ул-хонӣ. Баргаи 151; ۲۲۷. ص. محمد قاضى وفا كرمينگى. تحفة الخانى يا تريخ رحيم خانى.

⁷ Muhammad Vafa Karminagi. Tuhfat al-khani. Institute of History, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Main Manuscript Collection, Manuscript No. 5359, fol. 262b.

⁸ Ч.А. Стори. Персидская литература. Био-библиографический обзор. В трех частях. – Часть II. / Перевел с английского, переработал и дополнил Ю.Э. Брегель; Ответственный редактор Ю.Э. Борщевский. – Москва, 1972. – С. 917.

2. Oral testimonies of event participants, as well as the author's personal experiences and knowledge. The fact that the author incorporated oral testimonies he heard from friends and close associates about events that occurred during the writing process into the text demonstrates his effort to apply all his skills in composing the work. It is worth emphasizing that the inclusion of such important information from oral accounts clearly pleased the author.

An example of such memoirs and oral testimonies of event participants presented in *Tuhfat al-khani* is the account of Muhammad Rahim Khan's meeting with the Iranian Shah Nadir Shah in 1745. The author introduces this by stating that it is "according to the words of trusted nobles who were present at the shah's audience"⁹. At this meeting, the issue of dethroning Abulfayz Khan, the representative of the Ashtarkhanids, and replacing him with Muhammad Rahim Khan was raised by Nadir Shah. The author provides a detailed account in the work of Muhammad Rahim Khan's attitude toward Nadir Shah on this matter. According to him, Muhammad Rahim Khan emphasized that it was appropriate to govern the country through representatives of the Ashtarkhanid dynasty¹⁰.

The Author's Personal Experiences and Knowledge. The majority of Muhammad Vafo Karminagi's personal observations presented in the work are directly connected to the activities of the Manghit rulers, indicating the author's close relationship with the representatives of the Manghit dynasty. Indeed, the author gained significant attention at the Manghit court and participated in nearly all events held by Muhammad Rahim Khan. He was also honored by the Khan with valuable gifts, alongside many other dignitaries. This is evident from several remarks made by the author throughout the text. For example, the author mentions his participation in a special assembly convened by Muhammad Rahim Khan in Bukhara in 1756, after seizing power. During this gathering, Muhammad Vafo Karminagi read some of his own poems and was met with applause from the Khan¹¹.

Among his personal testimonies, Muhammad Vafo Karminagi reports the assassination attempt on Muhammad Rahim Khan in 1748, stating that he was a witness to this event¹². Indeed, the author describes the assassination attempt on Muhammad Rahim Khan that occurred during a celebration held on Ramadan 10 (September 1748), as follows: "Suddenly, the sound of a gunshot from the door on the eastern wall of the palace was heard by everyone, young and old alike. The deadly bullet fired from the gun flew like a star toward the Amir. As the blessed Amir leaned over the table to partake in the meal, the bullet struck his head approximately four

⁹ Мухаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат ул-хонӣ. Баргаи 101; ۱۸۴. ص. محمد قاضى وفا كرمينگى. تحفة الخانى يا تريخ رحيم خانى.

¹⁰ Мухаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат ул-хонӣ. Баргаи 101.

¹¹ Мухаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат ул-хонӣ. Баргаи 244; ۳۷۴. ص. محمد قاضى وفا كرمينگى. تحفة الخانى يا تريخ رحيم خانى.

¹² Мухаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат ул-хонӣ. Баргаи 145; ۲۲۸. ص. محمد قاضى وفا كرمينگى. تحفة الخانى يا تريخ رحيم خانى.

fingers above, hitting the wall. By the perfect protection of the Almighty and True Fa'iz, the Amir was saved from the enemy's vengeance. This tragic incident shocked the palace inhabitants profoundly, awakening their minds and opening the eyes of the Amir and his army to the threat. Following this salvation, the blessed Amir gave infinite thanks to the Creator and ordered the State Divanbegi and other close officials to search for those responsible." The author dedicates a separate chapter in Tuhfat al-khani titled "The Attacks of the Blessed Khan's Servants on the Auspicious Amir at the Great Ark and the Punishment of the Offenders Who Did Not Escape Salvation" to this event¹³.

In another passage, the author commemorates the death of Muhammad Rahim Khan, stating: "The author of these lines composed a noble couplet in the year 1172 AH (1758) about the death of the khan, so that it may remain as a lasting memorial on the tombstone of the world's protector for years to come." He concludes the first section of Tuhfat al-khani, dedicated to Muhammad Rahim Khan, with this statement¹⁴.

It is evident that Muhammad Vafa Karminagi exerted all his skill and talent in preparing Tuhfat al-khani. For this reason, in the work we encounter names such as Iskandar Zulqarnayn, Aristotle, Mahmud ibn Sabuktigin (997–1030), Amir Timur (1336–1405), Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi (d. 1454), Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur (1483–1530), Mawlana Nozim Hiravi, and Abdullah Khan ibn Iskandarkhan (1532–1598). Muhammad Vafa Karminagi provides examples from their activities and works throughout his text. Although he does not explicitly mention the sources of this information, it is undeniable that he drew upon the works of well-known historians of his time while preparing Tuhfat al-khani. In conclusion, it can be said that by relying on all the court documents of his era, his personal testimonies, and oral accounts, the author elevated the work's status as a primary source for writing the history of the 18th century. This ensured that Tuhfat al-khani would become a valuable reference for subsequent works.

Reference

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¹³ Muhammad Vafa Karminagi. Tuhfat al-khani. Institute of History, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Main Manuscript Collection, Manuscript No. 16, fol 146a-146b; .Муҳаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат ул-хонӣ. Баргаи 143; ۲۲۵. ص. محمد قاضى وفا كرمينگى. تحفة الخانى يا تريخ رحيم خانى. ص.

¹⁴ Муҳаммадвафои Карминагий. Тӯҳфат ул-хонӣ. Баргаи 290; . ص. محمد قاضى وفا كرمينگى. تحفة الخانى يا تريخ رحيم خانى. ص. ۴۴۵

3. Muhammad Vafa Karminagi. Tuhfat al-khani. Institute of History, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Main Manuscript Collection, Manuscript No. 16.

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